
SOME THEOREMS ON THE DIVISIBILITY OF $N!$ FACTOR

A PREPRINT

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January 26, 2022

ABSTRACT

This document is a compilation of theorems on factorials, a brief proof of the relationship of factorials with multiples of 9 from $n! \geq 6$, and general.

1 Introduction

A factorial function is the operation where all positive integers from 1 to $n!$ must be multiplied. In search of the properties of module 9, during the investigation [1] Tarazona, E. J. A., Flores, S., and Marrero, P. F. (2021). when we realized that every factorial greater than or equal to 6 was multiples of 9 up to infinity, it was from this that we started to look for the rest of the properties that could appear.

2 Theorem 1

If $n \in \mathbb{N}/n \geq 6$, then $9|n!$

2.1 Proof

As we can see the base case implies that $n = 6$.

1. If $n = 6$, this proposition is $9|6!$; If we use the recurrence ratio of the factorial, which is $n! = n(n-1)!$, then we verify that:

$$6! = 6(6-1)! = 6(5)! = 720$$

From the above result we can say that:

$$9|6!$$

2. Let $k \geq 6$. We have to prove that: If

$$9|k! \rightarrow 9|(k+1)!$$

For the above we will use the direct method. Suppose $9|k!$, therefore $k! = 9c$, For any $c \in \mathbb{N}$ Now we notice that $k! = k(k-1)! = 9c$. So we have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} (k+1)[(k+1)-1]! &= (k+1)k! \\ &= (k+1)9c \\ &= 9c(k+1) \\ &= 9[c(k+1)] \end{aligned}$$

As $[c(k+1)] \in \mathbb{N}$, this shows that $(k+1)[(k+1)-1]!$ It's a whole multiple of 9, then $9|(k+1)[(k+1)-1]! = 9|(k+1)!$

Now we have proven that $9|k!$ Implies that $9|(k + 1)!$.

Finally by induction method we have shown that $9|n!$ For all natural $n \geq 6$. □

2.2 Corollary 1

If $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq 6$ then $k|n!$ with $k = 3, 4, 5$.

2.3. Proof.

By **Theorem 1** for $n \geq 6$, then

$$n! = \prod_{i=1}^n i = 3 \prod_{i \in [n]_3} i = 4 \prod_{i \in [n]_4} i = 5 \prod_{i \in [n]_5} i \quad (1)$$

where $[n]_s \equiv \{1, \dots, n\} - \{s\}$ for $n, s \in \mathbb{N}$.

AXIOM

Being commutative multiplication in $\mathbb{N}$. It is known that:

- if $n \geq 2$, then $2|n!$ □

3 Theorem 2.

If $n, q \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq q$ then $q|n!$

3.1 Proof

The base case determines that $n = q$, From this, we have to:

1. By recurrence ratio, we know that $n! = n(n - 1)!$ so if $n = q$, we've got $n! = q(q - 1)!$ and as we know $(q - 1)! \in \mathbb{N}$.
Then if we do $(q - 1)! = c$, where $c \in \mathbb{N}$ we can fundamentally verify that $n! = qc$, and from here we conclude that $n!$ it's a multiple of $q \therefore q|n!$ for $n = q$.
2. Let $n \geq q$. Now suppose that $q|k!$ i.e. $k! = qc$ for any $c \in \mathbb{N}$.
By recurrence ratio we have to $k! = k(k - 1)!$. We can see that:

$$\begin{aligned} (k + 1)[(k + 1) - 1]! &= (k + 1)k! \\ &= (k + 1)qc \\ &= qc(k + 1) \\ &= q[c(k + 1)]. \end{aligned}$$

As $[c(k + 1)] \in \mathbb{N}$, it is show that $(k + 1)!$ it is a natural multiple of q . Then we have to $q|(k + 1)!$ Now we've shown that $q|k! \rightarrow q|(k + 1)!$. □

3.2 corollary

If $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq q$ if $q|n!$ then:

- (i) $q^n|(n!)^n$.
- (ii) $q(n!)^m|q^{1-n}(n!)^{n+m}$.

3.3 Proof

3.3.1 (i)

if $n, q \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq q$ with $q|n!$, then $q^n|(n!)^n$.

The base case determines that $n = q$. From this, we have that:

- a) As we know $n! = n(n-1)!$, therefore $q! = q(q-1)!$, since $n = q$. Now, how $q \in \mathbb{N}$, We can say that $(q-1)! = b$, such that $b \in \mathbb{N}$. then we have that:

$$\begin{aligned}(n!)^n &= (qb)^n \\ (n!)^n &= q^n b^n.\end{aligned}$$

. therefore, it is evident that:

$$q^n | q^n b^n \therefore q^n | (n!)^n \text{ for } n = q.$$

- b) let $n \geq q$. For this case we will test if $q^k|(k!)^k$, then $q^{k+1}|(k+1)^{k+1}$. Now we will use the direct method. Suppose that $q^k|(k!)^k \therefore (k!)^k = q^k = c$, for some $c \in \mathbb{N}$. now we observe that $(k!) = k(k-1)!$, then also we can affirm that $(k!)^k = [k(k-1)!]^{k+1}$ therefore it is valid if we say that:

$$\begin{aligned}[(k+1)!]^{k+1} &= [(k+1)((k+1)-1)]^{k+1} \\ &= [(k+1)(k)!]^{k+1} \\ &= (k+1)^{k+1}(k!)^{k+1} \\ &= (k+1)^{k+1}(k!)^k(k!),\end{aligned}$$

And as by hypothesis we know that $q|n!$, for $n \geq q$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}[(k+1)!]^{k+1} &= (k+1)^{k+1} q^k c q d, \text{ such that } d \in \mathbb{N} \\ &= (k+1)^{k+1} q^k q c d \\ &= (k+1)^{k+1} q^{k+1} c d \\ &= q^{k+1} [(k+1)^{k+1} c d].\end{aligned}$$

therefore $q^{k+1}|(k+1)^{k+1}$.

in conclusion, by mathematical induction, we have proved that $q^n|(n!)^n$ for all $n, q \in \mathbb{N}$. □

3.3.2 (ii)

if $n, m, q \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq q$ with $q|n!$, then $q(n!)^m | q^{1-n}(n!)^n$.

- a) As we can see, the base case implies that $n = m = q$. In addition to the above, we know that $(n!)^{m+n} = (n!)^m (n!)^n$, from where also:

$$(n!)^{m+n} = [n(n-1)!]^m [n(n-1)!]^n.$$

therefore, therefore, as $n = m = q$, it is possible to say that $(n!)^{m+n} = [q(q-1)!]^q [q(q-1)!]^q$. Based on the above equality, we are finally left with the following:

$$\begin{aligned}q^{1-n} &= q^{1-q} [q(q-1)!]^{2q} \\ &= q q^{-q} q^{2q} [(q-1)!]^{2q} \\ &= q q^q [(q-1)!]^{2q} \\ &= q q^q [(q-1)!]^q [(q-1)!]^q \\ &= q [q(q-1)!]^q [(q-1)!]^q.\end{aligned}$$

And as $q \in \mathbb{N}$, then it is valid to say that $[(q-1)!]^q = c$ such that $c \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore:

$$q^{1-n} (n!)^{m+n} = q [q(q-1)!]^q c.$$

In this case we study $n = m = q$, finally we have that

$$q^{1-n} (n!)^{m+n} = q [n(n-1)!]^m c.$$

From the above we conclude that $q(n!)^m | q^{1-n} (n!)^{m+n}$ for $n = m = q$.

b) Case $n \geq m \geq q$. The objective in this case is to prove that

$$q(k!)^m | q^{1-k}(k!)^{m+k} \Rightarrow q[(k+1)!]^m | q^{1-(k+1)}[(k+1)!]^{m+k+1}.$$

Now suppose that $q(k!)^m | q^{1-k}(k!)^{m+k} \therefore q^{1-k}(k!)^{m+k} = q(k!)^m b$, for some $b \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, by factorial recurrence relationship, we can say that:

$$q^{1-k}(k!)^{m+k} = q^{1-k}[k(k-1)!]^{m+k}$$

from the above equality we have that

$$\begin{aligned} q^{1-(k+1)}[(k+1)!]^{m+(k+1)} &= q^{1-k}[(k+1)((k+1)-1)!]^{m+(k+1)} \\ &= q^{-k}[(k+1)k!]^{m+k+1} \\ &= q^{-k}(k+1)^{m+k+1}(k!)^{m+k+1} \\ &= q^{-k}(k+1)^{m+k+1}(k!)^{m+k}(k!). \end{aligned}$$

According to **Theorem 2**, because $k, q \in \mathbb{N} / k \geq q \therefore q|k!$ ergo:

$$\begin{aligned} q^{1-(k+1)}[(k+1)!]^{m+(k+1)} &= q^{-k}(k+1)^{m+k+1}(k!)^{m+k}qc, \quad c \in \mathbb{N} \\ &= q^{1-k}(k!)^{m+k}(k+1)^{m+k+1}c \\ &= q(k!)^m b(k+1)^{m+k+1}c \\ &= q(k+1)^m (k!)^m (k+1)^{m+1}bc = q[(k+1)k!]^m (k+1)^{m+1}bc. \end{aligned}$$

And by the recurrence relation of the factorials, we know that

$$(k+1)! = (k+1)k!/k \in \mathbb{N} \therefore q^{1-(k+1)}[(k+1)!]^{m+(k+1)} = q[(k+1)!]^m (k+1)^{m+1}bc,$$

from where it is evident that $(k+1)^{m+1}bc = d$ such that $d \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore, we finally have that

$$q^{1-(k+1)}[(k+1)!]^{m+(k+1)} = q[(k+1)!]^m d.$$

From the above we conclude that $q[(k+1)!]^m | q^{1-(k+1)}[(k+1)!]^{m+(k+1)}$ for $n \geq m \geq q$. in this way by mathematical induction we have proved **(ii)**. □

4 Special Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Dr. Samuel Flores for his guidance during our research, for his ideas and corrections, for his patience and support.

Bibliography

- [1] E. J. A. Tarazona, S. Flores, and P. F. Marrero. Matriz_e_phi^9. clasificación de números enteros. algebra primordial. *Revista MATUA ISSN: 2389-7422*, 8(1):10–45, 2021.